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Contribution to the description of *Cucullia ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024 (Lepidoptera: Cuculliinae)

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Abstract. The comparison of *Cucullia ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024 and *Cucullia umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908 is given as a contribution to the description of *C. ilniczkyi*, with taxonomical and zoogeographical comments. They are illustrated with three-colour and label figures, the genitalia are presented with three monochromatic figures.

Keywords. *Cucullia*, Mongolia, China, taxonomy.

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Introduction

Since the diagnosis chapter in the original description of *Cucullia ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024 did not contain the comparison with the very similar and close relative, another taxon of the *Cucullia umbratica* species group, it became necessary to supplement the diagnosis by comparing *Cucullia ilniczkyi* with the taxon *Cucullia umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908. This short article serves this purpose, augmented with taxonomic and zoogeographical notes.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein are as follows: MfN = collection of Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin, Germany; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary). Other abbreviations used: RL = genitalia slide prepared by László Ronkay; GYP = genitalia slide prepared by Péter Gyulai; m = male; HT = holotype; CT = cotype.

Taxonomical and zoogeographical part

After the description and publication of *Cucullia ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024, the question arose that in its description, the diagnosis section omitted the very similar *Cucullia umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908 in external and genital morphology. The reason for this was that although this taxon was originally described as an independent species, Ronkay & Ronkay (2009) in their large summary work on *Cucullia* Schrank, 1802, synonymised both *C. umbratica clarior* Fuchs, 1904 and *C. umbratica lampra* to the species *C. umbratica* (Linnaeus, 1758).

This publication does not aim to clarify the taxonomic problems of the western Palearctic *C. umbratica umbratica* and the central Asian *C. umbratica clarior*, especially since Ronkay & Ronkay (2009) synonymized the latter one to the nominotypical taxon, which idea is acceptable.

C. lampra was originally described as a separate species by Püngeler as *Empusada (Cucullia) lampra* from the Aksu site (now in Xinjiang Uighur, China) based on two male specimens. Ronkay & Ronkay (1994) downgraded it to the subspecies of *C. umbratica*. Later, Ronkay & Ronkay (2009) synonymised it with *C. umbratica*, although its forewing pattern and genital morphology and its distinctive distribution pattern make it as a separate subspecies, as they have already corrected it in their most recent work (Ronkay & Ronkay 2024). In this publication, they correctly claim that „beside the Chinese Turkestanian *C. lampra*, there are two

unnamed taxa in eastern Afghanistan and Mongolia, although the genitalia of both sexes show no differential features“ and „the genitalia of the entire *umbratica* species group are very similar, even the externally strikingly different species“.

Diagnosis. *Cucullia ilniczkyi* (Fig. 1) differs from *C. umbratica lampra* (Figs 3, 4) by the darker wings, which are more conspicuous on the hindwings; the hindwings of *ilniczkyi* have a diffuse, broad marginal field, while the hindwings of *lampra* are almost clear white.

In the male genitalia of *C. ilniczkyi* (Fig. 7), the best distinctive features are the significantly weaker and longer uncus, the terminally inward curved harpe, the dorsally lower, ventrally less elongate triangular fultura inferior; while those are in the tube of the endophallus (vesica) the longer and prominent main diverticulum, terminated with a longer, but thinner strong cornutus, than in its congener (Figs 8, 9).

Since the description of *C. ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024, a few further specimens from NE Mongolia (Arhangay, Bulgan, Central, and Selenga aimak) have been dissected; however, these cannot be accepted as paratypes of *C. ilniczkyi*. This species is restricted to the low, dry, continental steppes in eastern Mongolia. Two similar male specimens with more variegated forewings have been studied from Qinghai, China, but with a much shorter and very broad uncus, very likely belonging to an undescribed close relative species.

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Figures 1–6. *Cucullia* sp. and ssp. adults and labels. **1.** *C. ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024, HT, m, E-Mongolia, Hentiy aimak, NE of Öndörhan, slide no. GYP 6157 (PGM); **2.** labels of *C. ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024, HT; **3.** *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, HT, m, Ost Turkestan, Aksu (= China, Xinjiang Uygur), slide no. RL 1965 (ex. coll. Püngeler, MfN); **4.** labels of *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, HT; **5.** *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, CT, m, Ost Turkestan, Aksu (= China, Xinjiang Uygur), slide no. RL 2957 (ex. coll. Püngeler, MfN); **6.** labels of *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, CT.

Figures 7–9. *Cucullia* sp. and ssp. male genitalia. **7.** *C. ilniczkyi* Gyulai, 2024, HT, m, E-Mongolia, Hentiy aimak, NE of Öndörhan, slide no. GYP 6157 (PGM); **8.** *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, HT, m, Ost Turkestan, Aksu (= China, Xinjiang Uygur), slide no. RL 1965 (ex. coll. Püngeler, MfN); **9.** *C. umbratica lampra* Püngeler, 1908, CT, m, Ost Turkestan, Aksu (= China, Xinjiang Uygur), slide no. RL 2957 (ex. coll. Püngeler, MfN);